

β -Diketones in Ring Formation. Part II.

BY UMAPRASANNA BASU.

An apparent exception to the hypothesis that a β -diketone preferentially reacts in its enolic form with a substance containing a reactive methylene group was observed in the course of a study of the reaction between benzoylacetophenone and cyanoacetamide where the yield of the condensation product, 3-cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone was found to be about 45 per cent. although the β -diketone is supposed to exist to the extent of 96 per cent. in the enolic form. (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 481). With a view to establish the validity of the above statement and to examine the influence, if any, of the adjacent substituent groups in the enolic ketone on the course of such reactions, the present investigation was undertaken. It has been observed that this anomaly could be best explained on steric considerations; a fuller detail and explanation of this statement has been embodied in the course of the present work.

Cyanoacetamide has been condensed with (1) benzoyl acetophenone, (2) benzoyl-*p*-methylacetophenone and (3) dipropionyl methane, $\text{Et}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{Et}$. It has been noticed that the condensation with benzoylacetophenone in presence of sodium ethoxide (Michael's way) gives an yield varying between 5 and 20 per cent. dependent on the conditions of the reaction. But by conducting the reaction with diethylamine (Knoevenagel's way) a better yield is obtained in the course of 3 days. The yield further increases to more than 70 per cent. when the concentration of the cyanoacetamide is increased. The rise of temperature again has an adverse effect on the yield. The condensation product, 3-cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone may also be obtained in about 75 per cent. yield by condensing α -ethoxy- ω -benzoylstyrolene, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OEt})=\text{CH}\cdot\text{COPh}$, an *O*-ether of benzoylacetophenone. The reason for the low yield in the former case may be attributed to the inhibiting effect of the β -phenyl group in the unsaturated ketone (I) (*cf.* Ingold and Powell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1976) and the difference in that again when sodium ethoxide or diethylamine is used as the condensing agent may be due to the greater reversibility of the Michael reaction when sodium ethoxide is used as observed by Ingold and Perren (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1416; *cf.* also Ingold, Perren and Thorpe,

ibid., 1770) who found that the condensation which takes place in the presence of piperidine (or diethylamine) is reversed to some extent by sodium ethoxide, particularly in the case where the retrograde reaction is more pronounced.

The β -diketone, benzoyl-*p*-methylacetophenone may exist in the two enolic forms (II) and (III) and may evidently give rise to two different condensation products (IV) and (V). Condensing the diketone with cyanoacetamide in presence of diethylamine, a product melting indifferently between 245 and 280° (evidently a mixture) was isolated during the course of a week. On fractional crystallisation from acetic acid the main crop (66 per cent.), 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (IV), m. p. 266-267° separated out. Its constitution was ascertained by direct comparison with a known specimen of the substance (Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 335). This on hydrolysis with 80 per cent. sulphuric acid gave 4-phenyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone, m. p. 226-28°. The other crop of the condensation product, 3-cyano-6-phenyl-4-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone (V), m. p. 311-12°, on hydrolysis gave 6-phenyl-4-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone, m. p. 237-239°. In this case the total yield was found to be still lower as expected and even in the condensation product the main crop was derived from the enol (II) evidently due to the greater inhibiting effect of β -*p*-tolyl group as present in (III), on such condensation. That the reaction had taken place through the enolic phase was evident by the isolation of only 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone from the condensation product of cyanoacetamide with α -methoxy- ω -*p*-tolyl styrolene, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OMe})=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Me}$ an O-ether of the β -diketone. Here also using one and half times the theoretical quantity of cyanoacetamide a better yield of the condensation product, calculated on the diketone employed was obtained.

The condensation product 3-cyano-4: 6-diethyl-2-pyridone (VI), from dipropionylmethane under the conditions described later, crystallised out from the reaction mixture after 3 hours and the total yield was 90 per cent. of the theory. But acetylacetone under

similar conditions affords 3-cyano- ψ -lutidostyryl (VII, X=CN) within two to three minutes and the yield is almost quantitative. This difference between the two cases may also be accounted for by the effect of the heavier substituent (ethyl) in the enolic ketone (VIII) than the methyl in the analogous ketone (IX). On this consideration the action of cyanoacetamide on benzoylacetone is interesting to note. The β -diketone may exist in the two enolic forms (X) and (XI) the former predominating over the other according to Scheiber and Herold (*Annalen*, 1914, 405, 295) but in its condensation the main product is 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XII, X=CN) (Basu, *loc. cit.*) indicating a greater activity of the latter enol towards cyanoacetamide. This is in agreement with the former conclusion that a heavier group (phenyl) in the enol (X) inhibits the reaction and the reason for the occurrence of (XII) is that as the condensation proceeds and as the latter enol readily reacts, more of it is formed from the other with which it is in dynamic equilibrium and consequently the main product of the reaction is derived from the enol which is supposed to be originally present in the system in small quantity. All these are in complete agreement with the view expressed by Ingold, Perrin and Thorpe, (*loc. cit.*) that in Michael's reaction "the presence of a β -substituent considerably reduces the tendency towards condensation. The effect is a spatial one, the larger the group, the stronger is the inhibition." Further work to study the effect of other substituent is in progress.

Considering certain conditions which govern the occurrence of a Michael reaction between a β -diketone and cyanoacetamide, it is also of interest to have an idea of the part taken by the methylene group of the cyanoacetamide molecule in all such condensations. So it

was found necessary to study the influence exerted individually by the substituents of the methylene carbon atom of the acetic ester residue (XIII).

Accordingly malonamide, $\text{CH}_2(\text{CONH}_2)_2$, was condensed with acetylacetone in the usual way when the known 4:6-dimethyl-2-pyridone-3-carbonamide (VII, $\text{X}=\text{CONH}_2$) separated after 3 days, the total yield being about 60 per cent. The compound was first synthesised by Knoevenagel and Cremer (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 239) from malonamide and aminoacetylacetone. Again the activity of ethyl cyanoacetate in such condensations has already been studied by Simonsen and Naik (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 793) who by condensing acetylacetone and ethyl cyanoacetate (piperidine) isolated mainly ethyl 4:6-dimethyl-2-pyridone-3-carboxylate (VII, $\text{X}=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) in 44 per cent. yield after several hours' heating. Benzoylacetone when similarly treated with ethyl cyanoacetate gave a crystalline substance, m.p. $216-17^\circ$ which on hydrolysis with 80 per cent. sulphuric acid afforded the known 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIV), m.p. $180-81^\circ$. (Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2223) and evidently the crystalline substance must have been ethyl 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone-3-carboxylate (XII, $\text{X}=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$).

It would hence seem probable that the rate of the reaction would further increase if the carbethoxy group be again replaced by another cyano-group. This has been found to be the case. For the reaction between malononitrile, $\text{CH}_2(\text{CN})_2$, and acetylacetone was found to be so vigorous and instantaneous that the reaction mixture had to be well cooled before the addition of the condensing agent and the product, almost pure 3-cyano- ψ -lutidostyryl (VII, $\text{X}=\text{CN}$) separated out within a few seconds (total yield=75-80 per cent.). Similarly in the case of benzoylacetone the condensation product crystallised out within 15-20 minutes by conducting the reaction at $20-25^\circ$. But unlike the condensation product from cyanoacetamide it consisted mainly of 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone, m.p. 310° (XII, $\text{X}=\text{CN}$), since the crystallised portion melted at 306° and the small amount, that was isolated from the mother-liquor on acidification, though melted indifferently between 240 and 260° afforded the known 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XIV) in good yield. The formation of the pyridone derivatives in the latter cases is similar to that investigated

by Simonsen and Naik (*loc. cit.*) and it may be said that the cyano- and the carbonyl-groups in (XV) have undergone the intramolecular change through the intermediate formation of an enol (XVI).

When one of the above negative groups is substituted by phenyl or chlorine, (as in phenylacetone, phenylacetamide or chloroacetamide) acetylacetone could not be induced to react with any of them under the usual conditions. Even on keeping the reaction mixture for 3—4 weeks and then heating it the amides could be recovered unchanged. Thus the evidence obtained from these observations indicates that the cyano-group is by far the more effective than any other group and that the reactivity of the methylene carbon atom depends on the total negative character of both the substituents and that if this does not reach a certain limit, the reactivity of the methylene group vanishes at least with respect to β-diketones.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1. *Benzoylacetophenone and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone.*

The β-diketone was prepared by the method described in "Organic Syntheses", Vol. VIII, p. 60; yield 80%; m.p. 77-78° on crystallisation from 95 per cent. alcohol.

(i) *By Michael's method.*—An alcoholic solution of benzoylacetophenone (11.2 g.) was added to the suspension of sodiocyanoacetamide prepared by adding an alcoholic solution of cyanoacetamide (4.2 g.) to the required quantity of sodium also dissolved in alcohol. At once a deep yellow coloured solution was obtained and the crystalline sodium salt that separated out was left overnight at the room temperature. Next day water was added to make a clear solution, which on acidification gave a crystalline precipitate. This was filtered, well washed with alcohol and ether when 3-cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone, m.p. 320° (Basu, *loc. cit.*) was obtained only in 5% yield. From the washed liquor benzoylacetophenone was recovered unchanged. Conducting the reaction at 60° for 24 hours, so that the sodium salt of the β-diketone remains in solution, a somewhat better yield (18-20%) may be obtained but the β-diketone

at the same time undergoes partial hydrolysis to its components, as smell of ethyl benzoate is distinctly perceived in the washed liquor.

(ii) *By Knoevenagel's method.*—This has been already studied (Basu, *loc. cit.*) but in the present case the reaction at the room temperature (32-33°) is described. To an alcoholic solution of molecular quantities of benzoylacetophenone and cyanoacetamide a few c.c. of diethylamine was added. After 2 days, the shining crystals that had separated out was filtered off and the mother-liquor with the addition of a few more drops of diethylamine was again left overnight. Next day another crop separated when the solution was acidified. The total solid (yield, 65%) was filtered, washed well with alcohol and ether. Using one and half times the theoretical quantity of cyanoacetamide, the yield was 55 per cent. (calculated on the diketone employed) when the reaction was conducted at 100° for 6 to 8 hours and to more than 70 per cent. when conducted at the room temperature for more than 3 days.

(iii) *From O-Ether of Dibenzoylmethane.*—*o*-Ethoxy-*o*-benzoylstyrolene, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OEt})=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{Ph}$, was prepared according to Ruhemann and Watson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 88, 462) and obtained as a yellow oil, b.p. 214-15°/14 mm. An alcoholic solution of the ether (8.4 g.) was gradually added with shaking to a suspension of sodiocyanoacetamide prepared from cyanoacetamide (2.8 g.) in hot alcohol and sodium (0.77 g.) also dissolved in absolute alcohol. The colour of the mixture turned brown and it was left overnight. After 3 days, water was added, the sodium salt was decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid and the product was filtered, well washed with alcohol and ether when 3-cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone, (m.p. 320°, 7 g.) was obtained. (Found: N, 10.15. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON}_2$ requires N, 10.3 per cent.).

2-Benzoyl-p-methylacetophenone and Cyanoacetamide. Formation of 3-Cyano-4-phenyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone (IV) and 3-Cyano-6-phenyl-4-p-tolyl-2-pyridone (V).

(i) The β -diketone was prepared from benzal-*p*-methylacetophenone (Weygand, *Annalen*, 1927, 459, 113) and was obtained in light yellow crystals, m.p. 84-85°. The condensation was effected as usual by means of diethylamine at the ordinary temperature. The crystals which separated after 4 or 5 days were collected and washed with a little alcohol. A further quantity of diethylamine was added to the mother-liquor, and left overnight. The crystal separated was again collected and washed with a little alcohol. The operation was

repeated till no more crystals separated out and finally the mother-liquor was concentrated and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was filtered, washed with alcohol and ether to remove the unchanged β -diketone. The time required for the whole operation varied from 7 to 10 days and the total yield was about 80 per cent. The crystallised product was generally found to melt between 250° and 260° and the product from the mother-liquor between 240° and 280° . Evidently the condensation product consisted of a mixture of the isomeric pyridone derivatives which were separated by fractional crystallisation from acetic acid in which the solubility of the two was found to be almost equal. The main product (about 66%) melted at 267° on recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid. It was 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone as proved by direct comparison with a sample prepared by Barat (*loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 9.8. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.79 per cent.). The pyridone derivative was difficultly soluble in alcohol but readily in pyridine from which it separated in fine prismatic needles. It is also soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid and forms a salt with alkali. On gently heating the substance with sulphuric acid (80%), till the evolution of carbon dioxide ceased, and pouring the acid solution on ice water 4-phenyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone was obtained. On crystallisation from dilute alcohol it melted at $226-28^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 5.4. $C_{18}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 5.36 per cent.). It is also soluble in alkali and imparts a brown colouration to alcoholic ferric chloride.

After fractional crystallisation another crop, m.p. $311-12^{\circ}$, was isolated. It is moderately soluble in alcohol and more so in pyridine and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid but is precipitated unchanged on dilution with water, and forms a sodium salt when dissolved in warm sodium hydroxide. (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.79 per cent.). Most probably this is 3-cyano-4-*p*-tolyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone. A mixture of this and its isomer (m.p. 267°) in equal proportion melted at $240-42^{\circ}$. The pyridone derivative on hydrolysis in the usual way afforded 4-*p*-tolyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at $287-39^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 5.34. $C_{18}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 5.36 per cent.). Its alcoholic solution imparted a brown colouration to ferric chloride. Conducting the above reaction with an excess of cyanoacetamide, as in the previous case, an yield of about 52% was obtained.

(ii) *Condensation with O-Ether of Benzoyl-p-methylacetophenone.*
— $\bar{a}$ -Methoxy- α -*p*-tolylstyrolene, $Ph \cdot C(OMe) = CH \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot Me$ (*p*),

was prepared according to Weygand's method (*loc. cit.*) and obtained as a thick yellow oil, b. p. 221-223°/22 mm. Its condensation with cyanoacetamide was effected exactly in the same way as in the case of the previous ether. The solid isolated, on crystallisation from aqueous pyridine melted at 267-68°, not depressed by admixing with the compound, m.p. 267°, previously described and was evidently 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone. (Found: N, 9·61. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9·79 per cent.). On hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (80%) it also gave 4-phenyl-6-*p*-tolyl-2-pyridone.

Dipropionylmethane and Cyanoacetamide: Formation of 3-Cyano-4:6-diethyl-2-pyridone (VI).—The β -diketone was prepared from methyl ethyl ketone and ethyl propionate by the method of Fischer and Bartholomäus (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1979) and obtained as a colourless liquid of agreeable odour, b. p. 175-77°/754 mm.

Cyanoacetamide (4·2 g.) was dissolved in water by warming and dipropionylmethane (6·4 g.) was added with just enough alcohol to effect the solution. About 2 c.c. of diethylamine being added, the yellow solution was warmed up to 50° and kept at that temperature for more than 2 hours. The flask was then removed and left at the ordinary temperature when crystals began to separate and soon a sludge was obtained. This (5 g.) was filtered off after half an hour and the mother-liquor with the further addition of diethylamine (1 c. c.) was left overnight. Next morning it was concentrated and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a further crop (3 g.) was obtained (total yield, 90%). On crystallisation from rectified spirit it melts at 186°. (Found: N, 15·5. $C_{10}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 15·9 per cent.). It is easily soluble in alcohol, chloroform, acetone, benzene and moderately in warm water. It readily dissolves in alkali from which it is obtained unchanged on acidification. Concentrated sulphuric or hydrochloric acid dissolves it and from the acid solution it may be recovered on dilution with water.

Hydrolysis: Formation of 4:6-Diethyl-2-pyridone.—The condensation product (1·5 g.) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) at 150° for 3 hours. Excess of the acid being removed on the water-bath, the residue was dissolved in minimum quantity of water, filtered and the filtrate on neutralisation with solid sodium carbonate gave the pyridone in almost quantitative yield. Crystallising from water it was obtained in small needles, m. p. 61-62°. (Found: N, 9·9. $C_9H_{13}ON$ requires N, 9·3 per cent.). This is soluble in almost all common organic solvents and also in alkali and

dilute acid. The alcoholic solution of the substance imparts a brown-red colouration to ferric chloride.

Acetylacetone and Malonamide: Formation of 4:6-Dimethyl-2-pyridone-3-carbonamide (VII, X = CONH₂). The amide was prepared by shaking ethyl malonate with a concentrated solution of ammonia. Its condensation with acetylacetone was effected just as in the previous case using malonamide in place of cyanoacetamide. The known product 4:6-dimethyl-2-pyridone-3-carbonamide (Knoevenagel and Cremer, *loc. cit.*) separated out in the form of a crystalline sludge after about 3 days. A further quantity was isolated after keeping the mixture again for a day with the addition of a few more drops of diethylamine and after the acidification of the final mother-liquor (total yield, 60 per cent.). It crystallises from boiling water with a molecule of water of crystallisation, m.p. 224-25°. (Found: N, 15.1. C₁₈H₁₀O₂N₂.H₂O requires N, 15.2 per cent.). The compound on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave a good yield of ψ -lutidostyryl, m.p. 179-80°.

Acetylacetone and Chloroacetamide or Phenylacetamide.—A similar dilute alcoholic solution of chloroacetamide or phenylacetamide and acetylacetone in molecular quantities in presence of diethylamine did not afford any condensation product even after 3 or 4 weeks. On refluxing the mixture for 6 hours and evaporating the alcohol the amide was recovered unchanged. An attempt to condense phenylacetonitrile with acetylacetone according to the method of Simonsen and Naik (*loc. cit.*) met with no success.

Acetylacetone and Malononitrile.—The nitrile was obtained from cyanoacetamide according to Hesse's method (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1896, 18, 726) as a colourless liquid, b.p. 219-20°. A mixture of acetylacetone (5 g.) and malononitrile (3.3 g.) was cooled in ice and to it about 10 drops of diethylamine were slowly added. The solution at once turned red and became distinctly warmer when a yellow crystalline solid separated out. The flask was left in a refrigerator. Next morning the solid (5.5 g.) was filtered off and washed with a little cold alcohol. From the mother-liquor on acidification a trace (0.2 g.) of the product was isolated (yield, 77 per cent.).

On crystallisation from boiling water (charcoal) it melted at 289°, and was found to be 3-cyano- ψ -lutidostyryl (VII, X = CN) by direct comparison and from mixed melting point determination.

Benzoylacetone and Ethyl Cyanoacetate: Formation of Ethyl 4-Methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone-3-carboxylate (XII, X = CO₂Et). An

equimolecular mixture of benzoylacetone and ethyl cyanoacetate after about 12 hours' heating with a few c.c. of diethylamine under reflux on a water-bath gave rise to a light yellow crystalline solid in a very low yield which could not be increased on further heating. Crystallising from glacial acetic acid it melted at 216-17° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.9. $C_{15}H_{15}O_3N$ requires N, 5.5 per cent.). It is difficultly soluble in alcohol and dissolves in hot caustic soda solution. Its constitution was ascertained by its hydrolysis to the known 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (Bardhan, *loc. cit.*). The compound was heated with sulphuric acid (80%) for half an hour; the acid solution was poured over ice water, filtered and the filtrate was almost neutralised with sodium carbonate, and the solid on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 180-81°. (Found: N, 7.6. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.8 per cent.). Evidently the condensation product is ethyl 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone-3-carboxylate (XII, X=CO₂Et).

Benzoylacetone and Malononitrile.—To a cooled alcoholic solution of benzoylacetone (8.1 g.) and malononitrile (8.3 g.) diethylamine (1 c.c.) was added when the solution became dark red and warm. Within 15-20 minutes yellow crystals began to separate when the flask was left overnight in a refrigerator. Next day the crystals (6.6 g.) were collected and washed with little alcohol and ether; m.p. 306°. To the filtrate a few more drops of diethylamine were added and the solution left overnight. A small amount of the product separated out but the total solid (1.4 g.) obtained on acidification was filtered off, washed with alcohol and ether; m.p. 240-80°.

The main crop on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) melted at 810°, not depressed by an admixture with 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone (XII, X=CN). The mother-crop even on several crystallisation from acetic acid did not show any sharp melting point. It was then hydrolysed with sulphuric acid (80%) in the usual way when the known 4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone, m.p. 180-181°, was isolated in good yield. The cause of the indifferent melting point may be due to the presence of a trace of the isomeric compound 3-cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone.

The author wishes to express his appreciation to Prof. H. K. Sen for his kind interest taken, and also to Mr. C. Barat of this laboratory for kindly supplying him with some of the starting materials required in this investigation.